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EDUCATIONAL ASPECTS OF THE WORK OF BOBURNAMA

Abstract: This article discusses the role and importance of the work of Baburnama in the history of the Timurids.

Keywords: History, Timurid period, work of Baburnoma, creativity, creativity, critical process.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada “Boburnoma” asarining temuriylar tarixidagi o‘rni va ahamiyati haqida so‘z boradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tarix, temuriylar davri, “Boburnoma” asari, ijod, tanqidiy jarayon.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль и значение творчества Бабур-наме в истории Тимуридов.

Ключевые слова: История, период Тимуридов, творчество Бабур-наме, креативность, творческий процесс, критический процесс.

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The role of the work "Boburnoma" in the study of the history of the Timurids in world educational and scientific research institutions, the modeling and design of the educational process, and the strategy of developing the work's unique qualities and attention to the ancestors. -research is being conducted. In this respect, the role of "Boburnoma" in the study of the history of the Timurids, raising the quality of education to the international level, he was a talented commander and statesman, a talented poet and writer, art, literature and special attention is paid to scientific researches, as he was a famous scientist who knows the value of science.

When the monograph "Renaissance of the Timurids and "Boburnoma"" published by the "Fan" publishing house in 2022 by the well-known literary critic Burobiya Rajabova came into my hands, at first, this recognition of our President crossed my mind. I have witnessed many times that the head of our state always strives to talk with intelligent, scientific, creative people and highly values such dialogues. Because, according to the beliefs of the President, "scientist is a great career that is embodied by the light of God. This career will spread to the whole society."

In this sense, on the example of this new book, B.Rajabova, on the one hand, has justified the high trust of our President, and on the other hand, she has paid tribute to the noble efforts of our state and society to build the New Uzbekistan and create the foundations of the Third Renaissance. made a brief scientific-practical contribution. The fact that the publication time of the book coincides with the approved period of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" is a proof of the impartiality of the author's intentions, and his good deeds are aimed at the response.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2023 "On the wide celebration of the 540th anniversary of the birth of the great poet and scientist, famous statesman Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur" is a huge event with a logical basis in the spiritual life of our country. It's done.

In the decision, taking into account the national and universal nature of the works of our great ancestor, his great role and influence in increasing the intellectual and spiritual potential of our young generation, raising our children to be the creators of New Uzbekistan on this basis, Babur Mirza's scientific

and creative legacy to our country and the need for further study and promotion at the international level is emphasized.

These days, the auspicious date of the birth of our grandfather, the king and poet, is being celebrated in a systematic manner and on a large scale in our country and on a global scale, based on the Program personally approved by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. It is not for nothing that the works "Renaissance of the Timurids" and "Boburnoma" [3] came to the attention of a wide readership in such auspicious times.

At the beginning of his work, the scholar, according to Babur Mirza's interpretation, was praising the name of his "wise, mudabbira" mother, and the great poet and thinker Abdurahman Jami said: "There is no better friend in the world than a book, and the sorrow of the age is sad. cites the verse saying, "there will be no"[4]. At the same time, while getting acquainted with the book, we hope that this important work will not only be "good" and "sad" for its fans, but also that it will be a spiritual helper for the intelligentsia of our country and give wings to our youth. we were sure.

In the first chapter of her book, B.Rajabova provides a comprehensive understanding of the Renaissance and the Renaissance of the Timurids. While speaking on this subject, the author skillfully leads the reader from distant history to today's reality.

That is: "In order to strengthen the spiritual foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, the publication of books on historical and literary topics has been launched in the column "Literature of the Second Renaissance" [5], notes B. Rajabova.

In the monograph, the life and activities of our great ancestors, mentioned in the world-renowned work "Boburnoma" by the Timurid king, the founder of the great Babur dynasty, and charming poet Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, are interpreted in detail in connection with the cultural environment of the Timurid Renaissance.

In particular, it is very important that the author has researched interesting topics in 8 specific areas addressed in "Boburnoma". Here:

First, the Timurids are Renaissance period and statesmen - Amir Temur, Mirza Ulugbek, Sultan Husayn Boygaro, Babur Mirza;

secondly, the Timurid Renaissance period and creators - Sultan Husayn Boykara, Alisher Navoi,

Abdurahman Jami, Kichik Mirza, Amir Shaikhim Suhaili, Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Zainiddin Mahmud Vasifi, Atullah Husayni;

thirdly, the Renaissance of the Timurids and the Timurid queens - the creative works of Gavharshad Begim, the stewardship of Esan Davlat Begim, the tenacity of Khanzoda Begim;

fourthly, the development of science, literature, art, history and culture during the Timurid Renaissance;

fifth, the role of astronomy in the Timurid Renaissance - the importance of Samarkand, Mirzo Ulugbek and the observatory he built;

sixth, military work and tactics during the Timurid Renaissance;

seventhly, the issue of medicine during the Timurid Renaissance - "Dor ush-shifa" built by Alisher Navoi and paintings depicting the lively image of doctors;

eighth, trade and monetary relations during the Timurid Renaissance - the regulation and control of markets, and images related to the minting and circulation of gold and silver coins, most importantly, the themes of the revival of the Great Silk Road.[6] .

Among the nobles who are the pride of our nation praised by the author, Sahibqiran Amir Temur ranks first. The more proud we are of Amir Temur, the more worthy he is. It was the great Sahibqiran who started the Timurid Renaissance with his work and laid the foundations of our happy days tod.

LITERATURE

1. Kuychiyeva M.A. Tabiiy fanlar o'qituvchilarining kompetentligi va kasbiy layoqatini rivojlantirish masalalari // Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti Ilmiy axborotlari. - Toshkent, 2021. - №1-son. - B. 53-57.

2. Kuychiyeva M.A. Use of Interdisciplinary Relationships In The Formation Of Competences In Biology Students // CONVERTER 2021 www.converter-magazine.info. - P. 485-489. (№10. ISSN:0010-8189). (subscription@converter-magazine.info)

3. Kuychiyeva M.A. // Organization of Experimental Works on the Development of Professional and Methodical Competence of Future Biology Teachers // Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. Open Access, Peer Reviewed Journals. 2022. ISSN (E): 2795-739, - P.19-21. (№7. SJIF; IF-8.115) (www.geniusjournals.org)

4. Kuychiyeva M.A., Eshmatova D. Development of Professional and Methodical Competence of Future Biology Teachers in Extracurricular Activities // Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. 2022. ISSN:2776-0979, - P. 617-621. (№12. SJIF; IF-7.565). (<https://wos.academiascience.org>)